

**ON HIGHER MOMENTS OF DIRICHLET COEFFICIENTS
ATTACHED TO SYMMETRIC POWER L -FUNCTIONS OVER
CERTAIN SEQUENCES OF POSITIVE INTEGERS**

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Abstract

Let j be a fixed integer such that $2 \leq j \leq 8$. Let f be a normalized primitive holomorphic cusp form of even integral weight for the full modular group $\Gamma = SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$. Denote by $\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}(n)$ the n -th normalized coefficient of the Dirichlet expansion of the symmetric square L -function $L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)$ attached to f . In this paper, we are interested in the average behavior of the summatory function

$$\sum_{\substack{a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 + a_4^2 + a_5^2 + a_6^2 \leq x \\ (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6) \in \mathbb{Z}^6}} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 + a_4^2 + a_5^2 + a_6^2)$$

for x sufficiently large. In a similar manner, we also consider the mean square of coefficients of the Dirichlet expansions of two symmetric power L -functions attached to two distinct primitive holomorphic cusp forms over the same sequence.

1. Introduction

The Fourier coefficients of modular forms are important and interesting objects in number theory. Let H_k^* be the set of all normalized primitive holomorphic cusp forms of even integral weight $k \geq 2$ for the full modular group $\Gamma = SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$. Then the Hecke eigenform $f(z) \in H_k^*$ has the Fourier expansion at the cusp ∞ :

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_f(n) n^{\frac{k-1}{2}} e(nz), \quad \Im(z) > 0,$$

where $e(z) = e^{2\pi iz}$, and $\lambda_f(n)$ is the n -th normalized Fourier coefficient (Hecke eigenvalue) such that $\lambda_f(1) = 1$. Then $\lambda_f(n)$ is real and satisfies the multiplicative property

$$\lambda_f(m)\lambda_f(n) = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \lambda_f\left(\frac{mn}{d^2}\right),$$

where $m \geq 1$ and $n \geq 1$ are positive integers. In 1974, P. Deligne [5] proved the Ramanujan-Petersson conjecture

$$|\lambda_f(n)| \leq d(n), \tag{1}$$

where $d(n)$ is the classical divisor function. By Equation (1), Deligne’s bound is equivalent to the fact that there exist $\alpha_f(p), \beta_f(p) \in \mathbb{C}$ satisfying

$$\alpha_f(p) + \beta_f(p) = \lambda_f(p) \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_f(p)\beta_f(p) = |\alpha_f(p)| = |\beta_f(p)| = 1. \tag{2}$$

More generally, for all positive integers $l \geq 1$, one has

$$\lambda_f(p^l) = \alpha_f(p)^l + \alpha_f(p)^{l-1}\beta_f(p) + \cdots + \alpha_f(p)\beta_f(p)^{l-1} + \beta_f(p)^l.$$

It is an important topic to consider the average behavior of Hecke eigenvalues of cusp forms in various aspects (see, e.g., [13, 16, 36, 38, 52]). In 2013, Zhai [54] considered the average behavior of the power sum

$$U_j(f; x) := \sum_{a^2+b^2 \leq x} \lambda_f(a^2 + b^2)^j$$

for $x \geq 1, 2 \leq j \leq 8$ and $a, b, j \in \mathbb{Z}$. Indeed, he successfully proved that

$$U_j(f; x) = x\tilde{P}_j(\log x) + O(x^{\alpha_j+\epsilon}),$$

where \tilde{P}_j with $j = 2, \dots, 8$ are polynomials with degrees $\deg \tilde{P}_2 = 0, \deg \tilde{P}_4 = 1, \deg \tilde{P}_6 = 4, \deg \tilde{P}_8 = 13$, and $\deg \tilde{P}_j \equiv 0$ for $j = 3, 5, 7$. The exponents α_j are given by

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{8}{11}, \quad \alpha_3 = \frac{17}{20}, \quad \alpha_4 = \frac{43}{46}, \quad \alpha_5 = \frac{83}{86},$$

$$\alpha_6 = \frac{184}{187}, \quad \alpha_7 = \frac{355}{357}, \quad \alpha_8 = \frac{752}{755}.$$

Very recently, the results of Zhai were refined and generalized for all $j \geq 2$ by Xu [53], by using the recent breakthrough of Newton and Thorne [33, 34], along with some nice analytic properties of the associated L -functions.

Let $\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n)$ denote the n -th normalized coefficient of the Dirichlet expansion of the j -th symmetric power L -function $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$ (see Section 2 for more details). Fomenko [6] proved that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}(n) \ll x^{\frac{1}{2}} (\log x)^2.$$

Later, this sum were studied by many authors (see, e.g., [25, 29, 44]). The analogous cases for symmetric power lifting $\text{sym}^j \pi_f$ for large j were considered by Lau and Lü [30], and Tang and Wu [51].

On the other hand, Fomenko [7] studied the sum of $\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^2(n)$. Later, this result was improved and generalized by a number of authors (see, e.g., [50, 11, 31, 45]). Recently, Sankaranarayanan, Singh, and Srinivas [45] proved that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^3 f}^2(n) = c_1 x + O(x^{\frac{15}{17} + \epsilon}),$$

and

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^4 f}^2(n) = c_2 x + O(x^{\frac{12}{13} + \epsilon}),$$

where $c_1, c_2 > 0$ are some suitable constants. Very recently, Luo et al. [31] established the asymptotic formulas

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}^2(n) = \tilde{c}_j x + O(x^{\tilde{\theta}_j + \epsilon}), \quad 3 \leq j \leq 6,$$

and

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}^2(n) = \tilde{c}_j x + O(x^{\tilde{\theta}_j}), \quad j = 7, 8,$$

where $\tilde{c}_j (3 \leq j \leq 8)$ is a suitable constant, and $\tilde{\theta}_3 = \frac{551}{635}, \tilde{\theta}_4 = \frac{929}{1013}, \tilde{\theta}_5 = \frac{1391}{1475}, \tilde{\theta}_6 = \frac{979}{1021}, \tilde{\theta}_7 = \frac{63}{65}, \tilde{\theta}_8 = \frac{40}{41}$, respectively. In the same paper, the authors also proved that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) = x P_j(\log x) + O(x^{\theta_j + \epsilon}),$$

where P_j is a polynomial with $\deg P_3 = 0, \deg P_4 = 2, \deg P_5 = 5, \deg P_6 = 14, \deg P_7 = 35, \deg P_8 = 90$, and $\theta_3 = \frac{971}{1055}, \theta_4 = \frac{262}{269}, \theta_5 = \frac{3237}{3265}, \theta_6 = \frac{4923}{4937}, \theta_7 = \frac{7442}{7449}, \theta_8 = \frac{89771}{89799}$, respectively.

In [46], Sharma and Sankaranarayanan considered the asymptotic behavior of the sum

$$U_{f,j}(x) := \sum_{\substack{n=a^2+b^2+c^2+d^2 \leq x \\ (a,b,c,d) \in \mathbb{Z}^4}} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n)$$

for $j = 2$ for $x \geq x_0$, where x_0 is sufficiently large. In fact, the authors established the formula

$$U_{f,2}(x) = c_f x^2 + O_f(x^{\frac{9}{5}+\varepsilon})$$

for any $\varepsilon > 0$, where $c_f > 0$ is some suitable constant depending on f . Very recently, Sharma and Sankaranarayanan [47] established the asymptotic formulae for $U_{f,j}(x)$ with $j = 3, 4$. In fact, they proved that

$$U_{f,3}(x) = c_1 x^2 + O_f(x^{\frac{27}{14}+\varepsilon}),$$

and

$$U_{f,4}(x) = c_2 x^2 \log x + O_f(x^{\frac{160}{81}+\varepsilon}),$$

where c_1, c_2 are suitable effective constants depending on f . Afterwards, the author and his collaborators gave some refinements and generalizations concerning the above results of Sharma and Sankaranarayanan, the interested readers can refer to [14, 15, 17].

In [48], Sharma and Sankaranarayanan investigated another type of summatory function related to the coefficients of the symmetric power L -function

$$S_{f,j}(x) = \sum_{\substack{a_1^2+a_2^2+a_3^2+a_4^2+a_5^2+a_6^2 \leq x \\ (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6) \in \mathbb{Z}^6}} \lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}^2(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 + a_4^2 + a_5^2 + a_6^2),$$

with $j = 2$. In fact, they proved the asymptotic formula

$$S_{f,2}(x) = c'_{f,2} x^3 + O(x^{\frac{14}{5}+\varepsilon}),$$

where $c'_{f,2}$ is an effective constant. Very recently, Sharma and Sankaranarayanan [49] considered the asymptotic formulae for $S_{f,j}(x)$ for all $j \geq 2$, by using the celebrated work of Newton and Thorne [33, 34], along with some individual and averaged subconvexity bounds of associated L -functions. More precisely, for $j \geq 2$, they established that

$$S_{f,j}(x) = c'_{f,j} x^3 + O(x^{3-\frac{6}{3(j+1)^2+1}+\varepsilon}),$$

where $c'_{f,j}$ is some effective constant depending on f and associated L -functions.

Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform, and let $\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n)$ be the coefficients of the Dirichlet expansion of the j -th symmetric power L -function associated to f . Inspired by the above results, the aim in this paper is to consider the summatory function

$$S_{f,j}^*(x) := \sum_{\substack{a_1^2+a_2^2+a_3^2+a_4^2+a_5^2+a_6^2 \leq x \\ (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6) \in \mathbb{Z}^6}} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 + a_4^2 + a_5^2 + a_6^2), \quad (3)$$

with $3 \leq j \leq 8$. More precisely, we are able to establish the following result.

Theorem 1. *Let $S_{f,j}^*(x)$ be defined by Equation (3). For $3 \leq j \leq 8$ and any $\varepsilon > 0$, we have*

$$S_{f,j}^*(x) = x^3 P_j^*(\log x) + O(x^{\theta_j^* + \varepsilon})$$

where P_j^* is a polynomial with $\deg P_3^* \equiv 0, \deg P_4^* = 2, \deg P_5^* = 5, \deg P_6^* = 14, \deg P_7^* = 35, \deg P_8^* = 90$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_3^* &= \frac{79}{27}, & \theta_4^* &= \frac{241}{81}, & \theta_5^* &= \frac{727}{243}, \\ \theta_6^* &= \frac{2185}{729}, & \theta_7^* &= \frac{6559}{2187}, & \theta_8^* &= \frac{19681}{6561}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $f \in H_{k_1}^*$ and $g \in H_{k_2}^*$ be two distinct Hecke eigenforms. Define

$$S_{f,g,i,j}(x) := \sum_{\substack{a_1^2+a_2^2+a_3^2+a_4^2+a_5^2+a_6^2 \leq x \\ (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6) \in \mathbb{Z}^6}} \lambda_{\text{sym}^i f}^2 \left(\sum_{r=1}^6 a_r^2 \right) \lambda_{\text{sym}^j g}^2 \left(\sum_{r=1}^6 a_r^2 \right), \tag{4}$$

where $i, j \geq 2$ are two fixed positive integers. In a similar manner as that of Theorem 1, we are also able to prove the following theorem.

Theorem 2. *Let $S_{f,g,i,j}(x)$ be defined by Equation (4). For $i, j \geq 2$ any two fixed integers and any $\varepsilon > 0$, we have*

$$S_{f,g,i,j}(x) = c_{f,g,i,j} x^3 + O(x^{3 - \frac{2}{(i+1)^2(j+1)^2} + \varepsilon}),$$

where $c_{f,g,i,j}$ is an effective constant given by

$$\begin{aligned} c_{f,g,i,j} &= \frac{16}{3} L(3, \chi) \prod_{i_1=1}^i \prod_{j_1=1}^j L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f, 1) L(\text{sym}^{2j_1} g, 1) L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f \otimes \text{sym}^{2j_1} g, 1) \\ &\times \prod_{i_1=1}^i \prod_{j_1=1}^j L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f \otimes \chi, 3) L(\text{sym}^{2j_1} g \otimes \chi, 3) \\ &\times L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f \otimes \text{sym}^{2j_1} g \otimes \chi, 3) H_{i,j}(3), \end{aligned}$$

and χ is the non-principal Dirichlet character modulo 4, and $H_{i,j}(3) \neq 0$.

Throughout the paper, we always assume that $f \in H_{k_1}^*$ and $g \in H_{k_2}^*$ be two distinct Hecke eigenforms. Also, we denote by $\varepsilon > 0$ an arbitrarily small positive constant that may vary in different occurrences. The symbol p always denotes a prime number.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we introduce some background on the analytic properties of automorphic L -functions and give some useful lemmas which play important roles in the proof of the main results in this paper.

Let $f \in H_{k_1}^*$ be a Hecke eigenform of even integral weight k for the full modular group $\Gamma = SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$, and let $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n -th normalized Fourier coefficient. The Hecke L -function $L(f, s)$ associated to f is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} L(f, s) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f(n)}{n^s} = \prod_p (1 - \lambda_f(p)p^{-s} + p^{-2s})^{-1} \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{\alpha_f(p)}{p^s}\right)^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\beta_f(p)}{p^s}\right)^{-1}, \quad \Re(s) > 1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha_f(p)$ and $\beta_f(p)$ are the local parameters satisfying Equation (2). The j -th symmetric power L -function associated with f is defined by

$$L(\text{sym}^j f, s) = \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{j-m} \beta_f(p)^m p^{-s})^{-1}, \quad \Re(s) > 1.$$

We may expand it into a Dirichlet series

$$\begin{aligned} L(\text{sym}^j f, s) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n)}{n^s}, \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p)}{p^s} + \dots + \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p^k)}{p^{ks}} + \dots\right), \quad \Re(s) > 1. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Obviously, $\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n)$ is a real multiplicative function. In particular, for $j = 1$, we have $L(\text{sym}^1 f, s) = L(f, s)$. Let $g \in H_{k_2}^*$ be a Hecke eigenform. The Rankin-Selberg L -function $L(\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g, s)$ attached to $\text{sym}^i f$ and $\text{sym}^j g$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} L(\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g, s) &= \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^i \prod_{m'=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{i-m} \beta_f(p)^m \\ &\quad \times \alpha_g(p)^{j-m'} \beta_g(p)^{m'} p^{-s})^{-1} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g}(n)}{n^s}, \quad \Re(s) > 1, \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $\alpha_g(p)$ and $\beta_g(p)$ are the local parameters of g defined in a manner similar to that of f in Equation (2), and where f and g are not necessarily different. Similarly, $\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g}(n)$ is also a real multiplicative function. From Equation (2), it is not hard to find that

$$|\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n)| \leq d_{j+1}(n) \quad \text{and} \quad |\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g}(n)| \leq d_{(i+1)(j+1)}(n) \tag{7}$$

for all $i, j \geq 1$, where $d_\nu(n)$ denotes the ν -dimensional divisor function, which is defined as the number of ordered representations $n = n_1 \dots n_\nu$ with integers $n_1, \dots, n_\nu \geq 1$.

Let χ be a Dirichlet character modulo q . Then we can define the *twisted j -th symmetric power L -function* by the Euler product representation with degree $j + 1$

$$\begin{aligned} L(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \chi, s) &= \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{j-m} \beta_f(p)^m \chi(p) p^{-s})^{-1} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n) \chi(n)}{n^s} \end{aligned}$$

for $\Re(s) > 1$. In the analogous manner, we can also define the Rankin-Selberg convolution L -function attached to $\text{sym}^i f$ and $\text{sym}^j g \otimes \chi$ by the Euler product representation with degree $(i + 1)(j + 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} L(\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g \otimes \chi, s) &= \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^i \prod_{m'=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{i-m} \beta_f(p)^m \\ &\quad \times \alpha_g(p)^{j-m'} \beta_g(p)^{m'} \chi(p) p^{-s})^{-1} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g}(n) \chi(n)}{n^s}, \quad \Re(s) > 1. \end{aligned}$$

We may expand it into a Dirichlet series

$$\begin{aligned} L(\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g \otimes \chi, s) &= \prod_p \left(1 + \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g}(p^k) \chi(p^k)}{p^{ks}} \right) \\ &= \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g}(n) \chi(n)}{n^s}. \end{aligned}$$

It is standard that

$$\lambda_f(p^j) = \lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p) = \frac{\alpha_f(p)^{j+1} - \beta_f(p)^{j+1}}{\alpha_f(p) - \beta_f(p)} = \sum_{m=0}^j \alpha_f(p)^{j-m} \beta_f(p)^m,$$

which can be rewritten as

$$\lambda_f(p^j) = \lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p) = \tilde{U}_j(\lambda_f(p)/2),$$

where $\tilde{U}_j(x)$ is the j -th Chebyshev polynomial of the second kind. For any prime number p , we also have

$$\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g}(p) = \lambda_{\text{sym}^i f}(p) \lambda_{\text{sym}^j g}(p) = \lambda_f(p^i) \lambda_g(p^j). \tag{8}$$

As is well-known, to a primitive form f is associated an automorphic cuspidal representation π_f of $GL_2(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{Q}})$, and hence an automorphic L -function $L(\pi_f, s)$ which coincides with $L(f, s)$. It is predicted that π_f gives rise to a symmetric power lift—an automorphic representation whose L -function is the symmetric power L -function attached to f .

For $1 \leq j \leq 8$, the Langlands functoriality conjecture, which states that $\text{sym}^j f$ is automorphic cuspidal, was established in a series of important work by Gelbart and Jacquet [8], Kim [28], Kim and Shahidi [27, 26], Shahidi [43], and Clozel and Thorne [2, 3, 4]. Very recently, Newton and Thorne [33, 34] proved that $\text{sym}^j f$ corresponds with a cuspidal automorphic representation of $GL_{j+1}(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{Q}})$ for all $j \geq 1$ (with f being a holomorphic cusp form). From the work of about the Rankin-Selberg theory developed by Jacquet, Piatetski-Shapiro, Shalika [23], Jacquet and Shalika [21, 22], Shahidi [39, 40, 41, 42], and the reformulation of Rudnick and Sarnak [37], we know that $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$, $L(\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g, s)$, ($1 \leq i \leq j$) and its twisted L -functions have analytic continuations to the whole complex plane (except possibly for simple poles at $s = 0, 1$ if $\text{sym}^j \pi_f \cong \text{sym}^j \pi_g$) and satisfy certain Riemann-type functional equations. We refer the interested readers to [20, Chapter 5] for a more comprehensive treatment.

Let

$$r_k(n) := \#\{(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) \in \mathbb{Z}^k : n_1^2 + n_2^2 + \dots + n_k^2 = n\}.$$

In this paper, we are concerned with the function $r_6(n)$. From [49, Lemma 2.1], we learn that for any positive integer,

$$r_6(n) = 16 \sum_{d|n} \chi(d')d^2 - 4 \sum_{d|n} \chi(d)d^2,$$

where $n = dd'$, and χ is the non-principal Dirichlet character modulo 4, i.e.,

$$\chi(n) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ -1, & \text{if } n \equiv -1 \pmod{4}, \\ 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

We can also rewrite $r_6(n)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} r_6(n) &= 16 \sum_{d|n} \chi(d) \frac{n^2}{d^2} - 4 \sum_{d|n} \chi(d)d^2 \\ &:= 16l(n) - 4v(n) \\ &:= l_1(n) - v_1(n). \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

It is not hard to find that $l(n)$ and $v(n)$ are multiplicative since the non-principal character $\chi(n)$ is multiplicative. Note that

$$l(p) = p^2 + \chi(p) \quad \text{and} \quad l(p^2) = p^4 + p^2\chi(p) + \chi(p^2),$$

and

$$v(p) = 1 + p^2\chi(p) \quad \text{and} \quad v(p^2) = 1 + p^2\chi(p) + p^4\chi(p^2).$$

Let $3 \leq j \leq 8$ be any fixed positive integer. From the definition of $S_{f,j}^*(x)$, along with Equations (3) and (9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} S_{f,j}^*(x) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) \sum_{\substack{n=a_1^2+a_2^2+a_3^2+a_4^2+a_5^2+a_6^2 \\ (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6) \in \mathbb{Z}^6}} 1 \\ &= \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) r_6(n) \\ &= 16 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) l(n) - 4 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) v(n). \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

For the sake of simplicity, for $l \geq 1$, let

$$\prod_{\chi}^l L(\text{sym}^l f, s) := L(\text{sym}^l f, s - 2) L(\text{sym}^l f \otimes \chi, s),$$

which means that $L(\text{sym}^l f, s - 2)$ and $L(\text{sym}^l f \otimes \chi, s)$ occur in pairs.

Lemma 1. *Let j be an integer such that $3 \leq j \leq 8$. Let $f \in H_{k_1}^*$ be a Hecke eigenform. Define*

$$\mathcal{F}_j(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) l(n)}{n^s}.$$

Then

$$\mathcal{F}_j(s) = G_j(s) H_j(s),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} G_3(s) &= \zeta(s - 2) L(s, \chi) \prod_{\chi}^l L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^3 L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^2 L(\text{sym}^6 f, s), \\ G_4(s) &= \zeta(s - 2)^3 L(s, \chi)^3 \prod_{\chi}^l L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^6 L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^6 L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^3 \\ &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s), \\ G_5(s) &= \zeta(s - 2)^6 L(s, \chi)^6 \prod_{\chi}^l L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{15} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{15} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{10} \\ &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^4 L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_6(s) &= \zeta(s-2)^{15} L(s, \chi)^{15} \prod_{\chi}' L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{36} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{40} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{29} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{15} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^5 L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s), \\
 G_7(s) &= \zeta(s-2)^{36} L(s, \chi)^{36} \prod_{\chi}' L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{91} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{105} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{84} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{39} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{21} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^6 L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s), \\
 G_8(s) &= \zeta(s-2)^{91} L(s, \chi)^{91} \prod_{\chi}' L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{238} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f, s),
 \end{aligned}$$

and χ is a non-principal Dirichlet character modulo 4. The function $H_j(s)$ admits a Dirichlet series which converges uniformly and absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$, and $H_j(s) \neq 0$ for $\Re(s) = 3$.

Proof. Since $\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n)l(n)$ is a multiplicative function, and also satisfies the bound $O(n^{2+\varepsilon})$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$, for $\Re(s) > 3$, we have the Euler product

$$\mathcal{F}_j(s) = \prod_p \left(1 + \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(p^k)l(p^k)}{p^{ks}} \right). \tag{11}$$

We only give the proof of the case $j = 8$, since other cases can be handled by a similar argument. For $j = 8$, from [30, (13)] and [31, Lemma 2.1], we learn that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p) &= 91 + 232\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}(p) + 280\lambda_{\text{sym}^4 f}(p) + 238\lambda_{\text{sym}^6 f}(p) + 154\lambda_{\text{sym}^8 f}(p) \\
 &\quad + 76\lambda_{\text{sym}^{10} f}(p) + 28\lambda_{\text{sym}^{12} f}(p) + 7\lambda_{\text{sym}^{14} f}(p) + \lambda_{\text{sym}^{16} f}(p). \tag{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

For $\Re(s) > 3$, the L -function

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_8(s) &:= \zeta(s-2)^{91} L(s, \chi)^{91} \prod_{\chi}' L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{238} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f, s) \tag{13}
 \end{aligned}$$

can be represented as

$$G_8(s) := \prod_p \left(1 + \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{b(p^k)}{p^{ks}} \right). \tag{14}$$

It is not hard to find that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p)l(p) &= \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p)(p^2 + \chi(p)) \\
 &= (91 + 232\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}(p) + 280\lambda_{\text{sym}^4 f}(p) + 238\lambda_{\text{sym}^6 f}(p) \\
 &\quad + 154\lambda_{\text{sym}^8 f}(p) + 76\lambda_{\text{sym}^{10} f}(p) + 28\lambda_{\text{sym}^{12} f}(p) \\
 &\quad + 7\lambda_{\text{sym}^{14} f}(p) + \lambda_{\text{sym}^{16} f}(p))(p^2 + \chi(p)) \\
 &= b(p).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{15}$$

Putting Equations (11)–(15) together, for $\Re(s) > 3$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{F}_8(s) &= G_8(s) \times \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p^2)l(p^2) - b(p^2)}{p^{2s}} + \dots \right) \\
 &:= \zeta(s - 2)^{91} L(s, \chi)^{91} \prod_{\chi}^{\prime} L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{238} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f, s) H_8(s).
 \end{aligned}$$

By Equation (7) and the bound $l(n) \ll n^{2+\varepsilon}$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$, the function $H_8(s)$ converges uniformly and absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$. \square

In a similar manner, for $l \geq 1$, we define

$$\prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^l f, s) := L(\text{sym}^l f, s) L(\text{sym}^l f \otimes \chi, s - 2),$$

which means that $L(\text{sym}^l f, s)$ and $L(\text{sym}^l f \otimes \chi, s - 2)$ occur in pairs.

Lemma 2. *Let j be an integer such that $3 \leq j \leq 8$. Let $f \in H_{k_1}^*$ be a Hecke eigenform. Define*

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_j(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n)v(n)}{n^s}.$$

Then

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_j(s) = \tilde{G}_j(s)\tilde{H}_j(s),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{G}_3(s) &= \zeta(s)L(s - 2, \chi) \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^3 L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^2 L(\text{sym}^6 f, s), \\
 \tilde{G}_4(s) &= \zeta(s)^3 L(s - 2, \chi)^3 \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^6 L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^6 L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^3 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{G}_5(s) &= \zeta(s)^6 L(s-2, \chi)^6 \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{15} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{15} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{10} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^4 L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s), \\
 \tilde{G}_6(s) &= \zeta(s)^{15} L(s-2, \chi)^{15} \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{36} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{40} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{29} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{15} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^5 L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s), \\
 \tilde{G}_7(s) &= \zeta(s)^{36} L(s-2, \chi)^{36} \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{91} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{105} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{84} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{39} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{21} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^6 L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s), \\
 \tilde{G}_8(s) &= \zeta(s)^{91} L(s-2, \chi)^{91} \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{238} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f, s),
 \end{aligned}$$

and χ is a non-principal Dirichlet character modulo 4. The function $\tilde{H}_j(s)$ admits a Dirichlet series which converges uniformly and absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$, and $\tilde{H}_j(s) \neq 0$ for $\Re(s) = 3$.

Proof. Since $\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n)v(n)$ is a multiplicative function, and also satisfies the bound $O(n^{2+\varepsilon})$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$, for $\Re(s) > 3$, we have the Euler product

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_j(s) = \prod_p \left(1 + \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(p^k)v(p^k)}{p^{ks}} \right). \tag{16}$$

We only give the proof of the case $j = 8$, since other cases can be handled by a similar argument. For $j = 8$, from [30, (13)] and [31, Lemma 2.1], we learn that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p) &= 91 + 232\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}(p) + 280\lambda_{\text{sym}^4 f}(p) + 238\lambda_{\text{sym}^6 f}(p) + 154\lambda_{\text{sym}^8 f}(p) \\
 &\quad + 76\lambda_{\text{sym}^{10} f}(p) + 28\lambda_{\text{sym}^{12} f}(p) + 7\lambda_{\text{sym}^{14} f}(p) + \lambda_{\text{sym}^{16} f}(p). \tag{17}
 \end{aligned}$$

For $\Re(s) > 3$, the L -function

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{G}_8(s) &:= \zeta(s)^{91} L(s-2, \chi)^{91} \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{238} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f, s) \tag{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

can be represented as

$$\tilde{G}_8(s) := \prod_p \left(1 + \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{h(p^k)}{p^{ks}} \right). \tag{19}$$

It is not hard to find that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p)v(p) &= \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p)(1 + p^2\chi(p)) \\
 &= (91 + 232\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}(p) + 280\lambda_{\text{sym}^4 f}(p) + 238\lambda_{\text{sym}^6 f}(p) \\
 &\quad + 154\lambda_{\text{sym}^8 f}(p) + 76\lambda_{\text{sym}^{10} f}(p) + 28\lambda_{\text{sym}^{12} f}(p) \\
 &\quad + 7\lambda_{\text{sym}^{14} f}(p) + \lambda_{\text{sym}^{16} f}(p))(1 + p^2\chi(p)) \\
 &= h(p).
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Putting Equations (16)-(20) together, for $\Re(s) > 3$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_8(s) &= \tilde{G}_8(s) \times \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(p^2)v(p^2) - h(p^2)}{p^{2s}} + \dots \right) \\
 &:= \zeta(s)^{91} L(s-2, \chi)^{91} \prod_{\chi}^* L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{238} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f, s) H_8(s).
 \end{aligned}$$

By Equation (7) and the bound $v(n) \ll n^{2+\varepsilon}$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$, it follows that $\tilde{H}_8(s)$ converges uniformly and absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$. \square

Lemma 3. *Let $i, j \geq 2$ be any two fixed integers. Let $f \in H_{k_1}^*$ and $g \in H_{k_2}^*$ be two distinct Hecke eigenforms. Define*

$$\mathcal{F}_{f,g,i,j}(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f}^2(n)\lambda_{\text{sym}^j g}^2(n)l(n)}{n^s}.$$

Then

$$\mathcal{F}_{f,g,i,j}(s) = G_{i,j}(s)H_{i,j}(s),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{i,j}(s) &= \zeta(s-2)L(s, \chi) \prod_{\chi} \left\{ \prod_{i_1=1}^i \prod_{j_1=1}^j L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f, s) L(\text{sym}^{2j_1} g, s) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \times L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f \otimes \text{sym}^{2j_1} g, s) \right\},
 \end{aligned}$$

and χ is a non-principal Dirichlet character modulo 4. The function $H_{i,j}(s)$ admits a Dirichlet series which converges uniformly and absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$, and $H_{i,j}(s) \neq 0$ for $\Re(s) = 3$.

Proof. This can be proved by an argument similar to of Lemma 2.1 by noting that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\text{sym}^i f}^2(p)\lambda_{\text{sym}^j g}^2(p)l(p) &= \lambda_f^2(p^i)\lambda_g^2(p^j)l(p) \\ &= \left(1 + \sum_{i_1=1}^i \lambda_f(p^{2i_1})\right) \left(1 + \sum_{j_1=1}^j \lambda_g(p^{2j_1})\right) (p^2 + \chi(p)) \\ &= \left(1 + \sum_{i_1=1}^i \lambda_{\text{sym}^{2i_1} f}(p)\right) \left(1 + \sum_{j_1=1}^j \lambda_{\text{sym}^{2j_1} g}(p)\right) \\ &\quad \times (p^2 + \chi(p)). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the lemma. □

Lemma 4. *Let $3 \leq j \leq 8$ be any given integer. Let $f \in H_{k_1}^*$ be a Hecke eigenform. Define*

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_{f,g,i,j}(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^i f}^2(n)\lambda_{\text{sym}^j g}^2(n)v(n)}{n^s}.$$

Then

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_{f,g,i,j}(s) = \tilde{G}_{i,j}(s)\tilde{H}_{i,j}(s),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{G}_{i,j}(s) &= \zeta(s)L(s-2, \chi) \prod_{\chi}^* \left\{ \prod_{i_1=1}^i \prod_{j_1=1}^j L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f, s)L(\text{sym}^{2j_1} g, s) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times L(\text{sym}^{2i_1} f \otimes \text{sym}^{2j_1} g, s) \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

and χ is a non-principal Dirichlet character modulo 4. The function $\tilde{H}_{i,j}(s)$ admits a Dirichlet series which converges uniformly and absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$, and $\tilde{H}_{i,j}(s) \neq 0$ for $\Re(s) = 3$.

Proof. This can be proved using an approach similar to Lemma 3. □

Lemma 5. *For any $\varepsilon > 0$, we have*

$$\int_1^T \left| \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{12} dt \ll T^{2+\varepsilon}, \tag{21}$$

uniformly for $T \geq 1$, and

$$\zeta(\sigma + it) \ll (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{13}{42}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}, \tag{22}$$

$$L(\sigma + it, \chi) \ll (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{1}{3}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}, \tag{23}$$

uniformly for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \varepsilon$ and $|t| \geq 1$.

Proof. This first result is given by Heath-Brown [9], the second result is the recent breakthrough due to Bourgain [1, Theorem 5], and the third result follows from Heath-Brown [10] and the Phragmén-Lindelöf principle for a strip [20, Theorem 5.53]. \square

Lemma 6. *For any $\varepsilon > 0$, we have*

$$L(\text{sym}^2 f, \sigma + it) \ll (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{6}{5}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}$$

uniformly for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 2$ and $|t| \geq 1$.

Proof. The result follows from the recent work of Lin, Nunes, and Qi [32, Corollary 1.2] and the Phragmén-Lindelöf convexity principle for a strip. \square

We state some basic definitions and analytic properties of *general* L -functions. Let $L(\phi, s)$ be a Dirichlet series (associated with the object ϕ) that admits an Euler product of degree $m \geq 1$, namely

$$L(\phi, s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\phi}(n)}{n^s} = \prod_{p < \infty} \prod_{j=1}^m \left(1 - \frac{\alpha_{\phi}(p, j)}{p^s}\right)^{-1},$$

where $\alpha_{\phi}(p, j), j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ are the local parameters of $L(\phi, s)$ at a finite prime p . Suppose that this series and its Euler product are absolutely convergent for $\Re(s) > 1$. We denote the gamma factor by

$$L_{\infty}(\phi, s) = \prod_{j=1}^m \pi^{-\frac{s + \mu_{\phi}(j)}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s + \mu_{\phi}(j)}{2}\right)$$

with local parameters $\mu_{\phi}(j), j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, of $L(\phi, s)$ at ∞ . The complete L -function $\Lambda(\phi, s)$ is defined by

$$\Lambda(\phi, s) = q(\phi)^{\frac{s}{2}} L_{\infty}(\phi, s) L(\phi, s),$$

where $q(\phi)$ is the conductor of $L(\phi, s)$. We assume that $\Lambda(\phi, s)$ admits an analytic continuation to the whole complex plane \mathbb{C} and is holomorphic everywhere except for possible poles of finite order at $s = 0, 1$. Furthermore, we assume that it satisfies a functional equation of the Riemann-type

$$\Lambda(\phi, s) = \epsilon_{\phi} \Lambda(\tilde{\phi}, 1 - s)$$

where ϵ_{ϕ} is the root number with $|\epsilon_{\phi}| = 1$ and $\tilde{\phi}$ is the dual of ϕ such that $\lambda_{\tilde{\phi}}(n) = \overline{\lambda_{\phi}(n)}$, $L_{\infty}(\tilde{\phi}, s) = L_{\infty}(\phi, s)$ and $q(\tilde{\phi}) = q(\phi)$. We write $\phi \in S_{\varepsilon}^{\#}$ if it is endowed with the above conditions. We say the L -function $L(\phi, s)$ satisfies the Ramanujan conjecture if $\lambda_{\phi}(n) \ll n^{\varepsilon}$ for any ε .

From above, we note that the L -functions $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$ and $L(\text{sym}^i f \otimes \text{sym}^j g, s)$, and their twisted L -functions are the general L -functions in the sense of Perelli [35]. For these L -functions, we have the following individual or averaged convexity bounds.

Lemma 7. *Let χ be a primitive character modulo q . For the general L -functions $\mathfrak{L}_{\mathbf{m},\mathbf{n}}^{\mathbf{d}}(s, \chi)$ of degree $2A$ indicated above, we have*

$$\int_T^{2T} |\mathfrak{L}_{\mathbf{m},\mathbf{n}}^{\mathbf{d}}(\sigma + it, \chi)|^2 dt \ll (qT)^{2A(1-\sigma)+\varepsilon} \tag{24}$$

uniformly for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1$ and $T \geq 1$. Furthermore,

$$\mathfrak{L}_{\mathbf{m},\mathbf{n}}^{\mathbf{d}}(\sigma + it, \chi) \ll (q(|t| + 1))^{\max\{A(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon} \tag{25}$$

uniformly for $-\varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \varepsilon$.

Proof. This can be derived by following an argument similar to that of Zou et al. [55], which was originally deduced from Jiang and Lü [24]. □

3. Proofs of Theorems 1 and 2

We only give the proof of Theorem 1, since Theorem 2 can be handled by a similar approach. In this section, we only give the proof of the case $j = 8$ in Theorem 1 in detail, since other cases can be handled by a similar approach.

Proof of Theorem 1, Case $j = 8$. From Equation (10), we know that

$$S_{f,j}^*(x) = 16 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) l(n) - 4 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) v(n). \tag{26}$$

Firstly, we consider the sum $16 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^j(n) l(n)$. For $j = 8$, by applying Perron's formula [20, Proposition 5.54] for the generating function $\mathcal{F}_8(s)$ in Lemma 1, we get

$$16 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n) l(n) = \frac{16}{2\pi i} \int_{\eta-iT}^{\eta+iT} \mathcal{F}_8(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right), \tag{27}$$

where $\eta = 3 + \varepsilon$, and $6 \leq T \leq x$ is some parameter to be chosen later.

By shifting the line of integration in Equation (27) to the parallel line with $\Re(s) = \kappa := \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$, and using Cauchy's residue theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 16 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n) l(n) &= 16 \text{Res}_{s=2} \left\{ \mathcal{F}_8(s) \frac{x^s}{s} \right\} + O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right) \\ &\quad + \frac{16}{2\pi i} \left\{ \int_{\kappa-iT}^{\kappa+iT} + \int_{\kappa+iT}^{\eta+iT} + \int_{\eta-iT}^{\kappa-iT} \right\} \mathcal{F}_8(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \end{aligned}$$

$$:= x^3 P_8^*(\log x) + J_1 + J_2 + J_3 + O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right), \tag{28}$$

where $P_8^*(t)$ is a polynomial in t of degree 90. In fact, the residue of the integrand coming from the pole at $s = 3$ with order 91, which is derived from the factor $\zeta(s - 2)$.

Next we evaluate the integrals J_1, J_2 and J_3 . Let

$$G_8^*(s) = \zeta(s)^{91} L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{232} L_8(s),$$

where

$$L_8(s) = L(\text{sym}^4 f, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, s)^{238} L(\text{sym}^8 f, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, s)^{76} \\ \times L(\text{sym}^{12} f, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, s)^7 L(\text{sym}^{16} f, s)$$

is an L -function of degree $3^8 - 787 = 5774$.

For J_1 , by Lemmas 5 and 6 and Equation (24), along with Hölder's inequality, we have

$$J_1 \ll x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \max_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T} \left\{ T_1^{-1} \int_{T_1/2}^{T_1} \left| G_8^*\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right| dt \right\} + x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \\ \ll x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \max_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \left(\int_{T_1/2}^{T_1} \left| \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{12} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{12}} \right. \\ \times \left(\int_{T_1/2}^{T_1} \left| L\left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{232} dt \right)^{\frac{5}{12}} \\ \times \left. \left(\int_{T_1/2}^{T_1} \left| L_8\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} + x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \\ \ll x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \max_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \left(\max_{T_1/2 \leq t \leq T_1} \left| \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{1080} \right. \right. \\ \times \int_{T_1/2}^{T_1} \left| \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{12} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{12}} \left(\max_{T_1/2 \leq t \leq T_1} \left| L\left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{2774/5} \right. \\ \times \left. \left. \int_{T_1/2}^{T_1} \left| L\left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{5}{12}} \left(\int_{T_1/2}^{T_1} \left| L_8\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} + x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \\ \ll x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{-1 + (\frac{13}{42} \times \frac{1}{2} \times 1080 + 2) \times \frac{1}{12} + (\frac{6}{5} \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{2774}{5} + \frac{1}{2} \times 3) \times \frac{5}{12} + \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} \times 5774 + \varepsilon} \\ \ll x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{\frac{1340573}{840} + \varepsilon}. \tag{29}$$

For the integrals over the horizontal segments J_2 and J_3 , by Equations (22) and

(25), along with Lemma 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_2 + J_3 &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}^{1+\varepsilon} x^{\sigma+2} \left| \zeta(\sigma + it)^{91} L(\text{sym}^2 f, \sigma + it)^{232} L_8(\sigma + it) \right| T^{-1} d\sigma \\
 &\ll \max_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1+\varepsilon} x^{\sigma+2} T^{(\frac{13}{42} \times 91 + \frac{6}{5} \times 232 + \frac{1}{2} \times 5774)(1-\sigma)+\varepsilon} T^{-1} \\
 &\ll \frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T} + x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{\frac{95747}{60}+\varepsilon}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Combining Equations (27)-(30), we obtain

$$16 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n) l(n) = x^3 P_8^*(\log x) + O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right) + O(x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{\frac{1340573}{840}+\varepsilon}).$$

On taking $\frac{x^3}{T} = x^{\frac{5}{2}} T^{\frac{1340573}{840}}$, i.e., $T = x^{\frac{420}{1341413}}$, we get

$$16 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n) l(n) = x^3 P_8^*(\log x) + O(x^{\frac{4023819}{1341413}+\varepsilon}). \tag{31}$$

Now we compute the explicit form of the coefficients of the polynomial $P_8^*(\log x)$. From [19, (1.11)] we learn that $\zeta(s)$ has the Laurent expansion at the simple pole $s = 1$:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{s-1} + \gamma_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \gamma_j (s-1)^j,$$

where $\gamma_j, j = 0, 1, \dots$ are suitable constants. In particular, $\gamma := \gamma_0$ is Euler's constant.

By the Leibniz rule and the method for the computation of residue at the pole $s = 3$ for an integrand function, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 x^3 P_8^*(\log x) &= 16 \text{Res}_{s=3} \left\{ \mathcal{F}_8(s) \frac{x^s}{s} \right\} \\
 &= \frac{16}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{90!} L(3, \chi)^{91} L(\text{sym}^2 f, 1)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f, 1)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f, 1)^{238} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f, 1)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f, 1)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f, 1)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f, 1)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f, 1) L(\text{sym}^2 f \otimes \chi, 3)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f \otimes \chi, 3)^{280} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^6 f \otimes \chi, 3)^{238} L(\text{sym}^8 f \otimes \chi, 3)^{154} \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{10} f \otimes \chi, 3)^{76} L(\text{sym}^{12} f \otimes \chi, 3)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f \otimes \chi, 3)^7 \\
 &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{16} f \otimes \chi, 3) H_8(3) x^3 (\log x)^{90} + \dots + c_f^* x^3,
 \end{aligned}$$

where c_f^* is some suitable constant depending on f and various associated L -functions.

Similarly, for $j = 8$, by applying Perron's formula [20, Proposition 5.54] for the generating function $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_8(s)$ in Lemma 2, we get

$$4 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n)v(n) = \frac{4}{2\pi i} \int_{\eta-iT}^{\eta+iT} \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_8(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right), \tag{32}$$

where $\eta = 3 + \varepsilon$, and $6 \leq T \leq x$ is some parameter to be chosen later.

By shifting the line of integration in Equation (32) to the parallel line with $\Re(s) = \kappa := \frac{5}{2} + \varepsilon$ and using Cauchy's residue theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 4 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n)v(n) &= \frac{4}{2\pi i} \left\{ \int_{\kappa-iT}^{\kappa+iT} + \int_{\kappa+iT}^{\eta+iT} + \int_{\eta-iT}^{\kappa-iT} \right\} \mathcal{F}_8(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right), \\ &:= I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

since in this case there is no singularity in the rectangle obtained, and the integrand $\mathcal{F}_8(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ is analytic in this region.

$$\tilde{G}_8^*(s) = L(s, \chi)^{91} \tilde{L}_8(s),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{L}_8(s) &= L(\text{sym}^2 f \otimes \chi, s)^{232} L(\text{sym}^4 f \otimes \chi, s)^{280} L(\text{sym}^6 f \otimes \chi, s)^{238} \\ &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^8 f \otimes \chi, s)^{154} L(\text{sym}^{10} f \otimes \chi, s)^{76} \\ &\quad \times L(\text{sym}^{12} f \otimes \chi, s)^{28} L(\text{sym}^{14} f \otimes \chi, s)^7 L(\text{sym}^{16} f \otimes \chi, s) \end{aligned}$$

is an L -function of degree $3^8 - 91 = 6470$.

For the integrals I_2 and I_3 over the horizontal segments, by Equations (23) and (25), we have

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 + I_3 &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}^{1+\varepsilon} T^{-1} |\tilde{G}_8^*(\sigma + it)| x^{\sigma+2} d\sigma \\ &\ll \max_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1+\varepsilon} x^{\sigma+2} T^{(\frac{1}{3} \times 91 + \frac{1}{2} \times 6470)(1-\sigma) + \varepsilon} T^{-1} \\ &\ll \frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T} + x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{\frac{9790}{6} + \varepsilon}. \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

For the integral I_1 over the vertical segment, by Equation (24) and the Cauchy-

Schwarz inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 &\ll x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \max_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T/2} \left\{ T^{-1} \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| L\left(\frac{1}{2} + it, \chi\right) \right|^{91} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right. \\
 &\quad \times \left. \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \tilde{L}_8\left(\frac{1}{2} + it, \chi\right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} + x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} \\
 &\ll x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{\frac{6557}{4}+\varepsilon}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Putting Equations (33)-(35) together, we obtain

$$4 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n) v(n) = O\left(\frac{x^{3+\varepsilon}}{T}\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{\frac{6557}{4}+\varepsilon}\right). \tag{36}$$

Now we choose $x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{\frac{6557}{4}} = \frac{x^3}{T}$, i.e., $T = x^{\frac{2}{6561}}$, we get

$$4 \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_{\text{sym}^2 f}^8(n) v(n) = O\left(x^{\frac{19681}{6561}+\varepsilon}\right). \tag{37}$$

Combining Equations (26), (31) and (37), we get

$$S_{f,j}^*(x) = x^3 P_8^*(\log x) + O\left(x^{\frac{19681}{6561}+\varepsilon}\right).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1. □

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